

Synthesis and Characterisation of Some Di-*p*-tolyltin Dithiocarbamates

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Several new di-*p*-tolyltin dithiocarbamates of the formula $(p\text{-tolyl})_2\text{SnX}_{(2-n)}(\text{R}_2\text{NCS}_2)_n$ have been synthesized and characterized by analytical data, conductance, infrared, pmr and electronic spectral data. The ligand in these compounds is bidentate. In contrast to triorganotin dithiocarbamates they do not possess significant antimicrobial activity.

In recent years a large number of metal, organometal dithiocarbamates have been prepared with a view to establish structure—activity relationship. In continuation of the studies on diorganotin dithiocarbamates reported from this laboratory¹⁻³, we now report the synthesis and characterisation of several new di-*p*-tolyltin dithiocarbamates of the general formula $(p\text{-tolyl})_2\text{SnX}_{(2-n)}(\text{R}_2\text{NCS}_2)_n$ (where R_2NCS_2 = diethyl-, di-*n*-butyl-, morpholino-, piperidino-, pyrrolidino dithiocarbamates, $n=1$ or 2 ; $\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{N}_3, \text{NCS}, \text{NO}_2$ or other dithiocarbamate group). Antimicrobial activity of the compounds has also been evaluated *in vitro*.

Experimental

Sodium diethyl dithiocarbamate was obtained from the Alfa Inorganics, USA. Ammonium salts of other dithiocarbamic acids were synthesized by reported methods⁴. Di-*p*-tolyltin dichloride was prepared by redistribution reaction between tetra-*p*-tolyltin and tin tetrachloride⁵. Physico-chemical measurements were made as reported earlier².

Preparation of di-*p*-tolyltin dithiocarbamate (dtc) :

Di-*p*-tolyltin bis(dithiocarbamates) have been synthesized by insertion of carbon disulfide into a mixture of di-*p*-tolyltin dichloride and an amine in an appropriate solvent^{2,3}. In a typical experiment, a solution of morpholine (20 mmole) in acetone (10 ml) was slowly added to a solution containing di-*p*-tolyltin dichloride (5 mmole) and carbon disulfide (10 ml) in acetone (20 ml) at 20°, with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was further stirred for two hrs and filtered. Excess acetone was then distilled from the filtrate and the product precipitated by addition of excess of diethyl ether. The colourless solid was washed with diethyl ether and dried in vacuum, m.p. 174°. yield 75%.

Di-*p*-tolyltin bis(dithiocarbamates) and their monochloro derivatives of the formula $(p\text{-tolyl})_2\text{SnCl}(\text{R}_2\text{NCS}_2)$ have also been synthesized through

metathetical reaction between di-*p*-tolyltin dichloride and sodium or ammonium salts of dithiocarbamic acids in an appropriate solvent in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio². In a typical experiment, a mixture of sodium diethyl dithiocarbamate (10 mmole) and di-*p*-tolyltin dichloride (10 mmole) in benzene (20 ml) was stirred for two hrs. From the filtrate excess benzene was distilled under reduced pressure. To the residue excess of diethyl ether was added which yielded a colourless solid, m.p. 130-31°, yield 80%.

Compounds of the general formula $(p\text{-tolyl})_2\text{SnX}(\text{R}_2\text{NCS}_2)$ (where $\text{X}=\text{N}_3, \text{NCS}, \text{NO}_2$ or other dithiocarbamate group) have been prepared by interaction of $(p\text{-tolyl})_2\text{SnCl}(\text{R}_2\text{NCS}_2)$ with sodium or ammonium salts of X in 1 : 1 molar ratio leading to substitution of Cl by X . In a typical experiment di-*p*-tolyltin chloro diethyl dithiocarbamate (10 mmole), synthesized as above, was dissolved in a minimum quantity of chloroform and sodium azide (10 mmole) in the same solvent was added to it. The mixture was stirred for about two hrs. The precipitated sodium chloride was removed and the excess solvent distilled under reduced pressure. Addition of excess diethyl ether to the residue afforded the desired product which was recrystallized from the same solvent, m.p. 103°, yield 80%.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds are sharp melting, white or light yellow solid. They are fairly stable at room temperature, unaffected by atmospheric oxygen and moisture and readily soluble in almost all common organic solvents such as chloroform, benzene or acetone. Molecular weight of the compounds in freezing benzene and conductance measurements in acetone indicate the monomeric and non-electrolytic nature of the compounds in solution.

Infrared spectra :

The characteristic absorption frequencies of dithiocarbamate group have been identified

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR $(p\text{-tolyl})_2\text{SnCl}_{(2-n)}(\text{dtc})_n$

n	Compound dtc	m.p. (°C)	Mol. wt. Obsvd. (Calcd.)	Analysis % Obsvd. (Calcd.)			Infrared absorption frequencies (cm ⁻¹)	
				Sn	C	H	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$
2	diethyl	155	568 (597)	19.98 (19.93)	48.31 (48.24)	5.72 (5.70)	1480	990
1	diethyl	130-31	461 (484)	24.61 (24.56)	47.13 (47.06)	4.89 (4.95)	1500	975
2	morph	174	597 (625)	19.12 (19.04)	45.98 (46.08)	4.77 (4.80)	1475	990
1	morph	182	465 (498)	23.91 (23.87)	45.68 (45.74)	4.37 (4.41)	1480	990
2	pip	135	593 (621)	19.21 (19.16)	50.18 (50.24)	5.37 (5.48)	1470	980
1	pip	155	472 (496)	23.91 (23.97)	48.29 (48.34)	4.76 (4.83)	1490	995
2	pyrr	144	567 (593)	20.12 (20.07)	48.61 (48.57)	5.01 (5.06)	1470	980
1	pyrr	138	463 (482)	24.71 (24.66)	47.31 (47.25)	4.49 (4.56)	1480	990
2	di(<i>n</i> -bu)	102	694 (709)	16.73 (16.78)	54.21 (54.16)	7.13 (7.05)	1480	975
1	di(<i>n</i> -bu)	86	497 (540)	22.10 (22.02)	51.13 (51.06)	5.97 (5.92)	1500	980

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR $(p\text{-tolyl})_2\text{SnX dtc}$

X	Compound dtc	m.p. (°C)	mol. wt. obsvd. (Calcd.)	Analysis % Obsvd. (Calcd.)			Infrared absorption frequencies (cm ⁻¹)	
				Sn	C	H	$\nu\text{C}-\text{N}$	$\nu\text{C}-\text{S}$
N ₃	diethyl	103	463 (491)	24.29 (24.24)	46.37 (46.44)	4.83 (4.89)	1495	980
N ₃	morph	146-48	482 (505)	23.61 (23.56)	45.21 (45.15)	4.41 (4.36)	1480	990
N ₃	pip	128	487 (503)	23.71 (23.66)	47.76 (47.71)	4.69 (4.77)	1485	995
N ₃	pyrr	142	461 (489)	24.39 (24.34)	46.57 (46.63)	4.56 (4.50)	1490	995
N ₃	di <i>n</i> -bu)	90	497 (547)	21.81 (21.76)	50.51 (50.46)	5.82 (5.85)	1480	980
NCS	diethyl	124	489 (507)	23.51 (23.47)	47.39 (47.34)	4.77 (4.73)	1500	980
NCS	pip	146	483 (519)	22.89 (22.93)	48.61 (48.55)	4.59 (4.62)	1510	995
NOS	pyrr	146	463 (505)	23.51 (23.56)	47.56 (47.52)	4.39 (4.36)	1490	995
NO ₂	diethyl	134	488 (511)	23.34 (23.29)	44.69 (44.62)	4.67 (4.70)	1502	990
dedtc	pip	115	591 (609)	19.49 (19.54)	49.42 (49.26)	5.61 (5.58)	1470	980
dedtc	pyrr	144	581 (595)	19.97 (20.00)	48.47 (48.40)	5.42 (5.48)	1470	980
pipdtc	di(<i>n</i> -bu)	126	643 (665)	17.93 (17.89)	52.29 (52.38)	6.38 (6.32)	1470	980

(Table 2). From the strong C-N stretching absorption falling in the region (1510-1470 cm⁻¹), it is evident that the presence of an electron withdrawing group at the tin atom shifts the $\nu\text{C}-\text{N}$ mode towards higher frequency due to decrease of electron density. The presence of a single intense band for $\nu\text{C}-\text{S}$ in the region (1050-975 cm⁻¹) in the spectra of all the compounds supports the bidentate chelated behaviour of the ligand^{6,7}.

In thiocyanate substituted compounds, absorption bands at 2040, (850-820) and 480 cm⁻¹ are assigned

to ν asym-NCS, $\nu\text{C}-\text{S}$ and δNCS modes of vibration respectively, which are consistent with the nitrogen bonded thiocyanate group⁸. The spectral studies of azido substituted dithiocarbamates reveal an intense band at 2060 cm⁻¹, a medium band at 1310 cm⁻¹ and a band of weak intensity at 640 cm⁻¹ assignable to asymmetric, symmetric stretchings and bending modes of vibration of (-N=N=N) group respectively which are indicative of covalent Sn-N₃ bonding^{1,9,10}. In the spectrum of the nitrate compound, the absorptions at 1525-1500 cm⁻¹ 1240 and 840 cm⁻¹ are assigned to asymmetric, symmetric

and out-of-plane deformation modes of vibration of $-\text{NO}_2$ group respectively. A weak band at 975 cm^{-1} is due to $-\text{NO}$ stretching vibration. The data indicate a covalently bonded unidentate nitrate group¹¹⁻¹³.

Proton magnetic resonance spectra :

PMR spectra of the following two compounds were recorded in CdCl_2 at room temperature ($\sim 30^\circ$).

The spectra exhibit three groups of signals, due to phenyl ring, $\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$ and alkyl protons. The phenyl protons appearing as two doublets centered at ~ 7.2 and ~ 8.0 δ ppm due to *o-o*-coupling and alkyl protons in the form of a multiplet in the region (0.90-0.30) δ ppm indicate absence of abnormal rearrangement during the reaction course. A high value for $\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$ proton signals due to large electron drift of nitrogen π -electrons towards the carbon atom or increased $\text{C}-\text{N}$ bond order, suggests bidentate mode of coordination of the ligand^{8,14,15}.

Electronic spectra :

Electronic spectra of representative compounds were recorded in absolute methanol in the ultraviolet region. The absorption bands at $246 (\pm 4)$ and $280 (\pm 2)$ nm in the spectra of all the compounds are assigned to intraligand transition bands^{16,17}. A sharp splitting of the high energy band may be taken as an evidence of bidentate ligating behaviour of dithiocarbamate moiety in these compounds¹⁷.

The spectroscopic data suggest bidentate mode of bonding of the dithiocarbamate group in the compounds examined. A *cis*-octahedral configuration may be assigned to di-*p*-tolyltin bis(dithiocarbamates) while the monosubstituted derivatives may bear a trigonal bipyramidal geometry. The conclusion is in agreement with previous reports^{9,18}.

Antimicrobial activity :

The antimicrobial activity of the compounds was examined *in vitro* by two fold serial dilution method¹⁹ against three fungal species *Canidada albicans*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *Aspergillus fumigatus* and two bacteria *Streptococcus faecalis* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Sabourand's broth (g/l. distilled water, peptone 10.0, dextrose 20.0, pH

approximately 6.0) and nutrient broth (Peptone 0.5 g, NaCl 0.35 g, dextrose 0.1 g, K_2HPO_4 0.368 g, KH_2PO_4 10.132 g, yeast extract 60.15 g, lablemco 0.15 g and distilled water 100 ml, pH 7.2) were used as test media for fungi and bacteria respectively. The fungi were incubated at $28(\pm 1)^\circ$ and bacteria at 37° . Incubation period for bacteria and the fungi *C. albicans* was 24 hrs, for *A. fumigatus* 48 hrs and for *T. mentagrophytes* 96 hrs. The maximum concentration of the compound tested was 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. All the tests were carried out in duplicate.

It is observed that the compounds under investigation do not significantly suppress the microbial growth which is in accordance with the reported observation that diorganotin in general possess poor activity²⁰.

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